

AN EXPLICIT FORMULA FOR HECKE L -FUNCTIONS

Xian-Jin Li¹

Department of Mathematics, Brigham Young University, Provo, Utah 84602, USA
 xianjin@math.byu.edu

Received: 1/2/07, Accepted: 8/15/07, Published: 8/1/08

Abstract

In 1997 the author found an interesting sequence of numbers that are related to zeros of the Riemann zeta function. In this paper we study a similar sequence of numbers, which are related zeros of L -functions associated with modular forms of weight $k > 2$. In particular, an explicit formula is obtained for this sequence of numbers. It generalizes a previous result of the author where only the weight 2 case was considered.

– Dedicated to Melvyn Nathanson on the occasion of his 60th Birthday

1. Introduction

Let k and N be positive integers with $k > 2$, and let χ be a Dirichlet character of modulus N with $\chi(-1) = (-1)^k$ and with conductor \mathfrak{f} . We denote by $S_k(N, \chi)$ the space of cusp forms of weight k and character χ for the Hecke congruence subgroup $\Gamma_0(N)$ of level N . That is, f belongs to $S_k(N, \chi)$ if and only if f is holomorphic in the upper half-plane, satisfies

$$f\left(\frac{az+b}{cz+d}\right) = \chi(d)(cz+d)^k f(z)$$

for all $\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in \Gamma_0(N)$, satisfies the usual regularity conditions at the cusps of $\Gamma_0(N)$, and vanishes at each cusp of $\Gamma_0(N)$.

The Hecke operators T_n are given by

$$(T_n f)(z) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{ad=n} \chi(a) a^k \sum_{0 \leq b < d} f\left(\frac{az+b}{d}\right). \tag{1}$$

¹Research supported by National Security Agency H98230-06-1-0061

A function f in $S_k(N, \chi)$ is called a Hecke eigenform if $T_n f = \lambda(n)f$ for all positive integers n with $(n, N) = 1$. The Fricke involution W is defined by

$$(Wf)(z) = N^{-k/2} z^{-k} f(-1/Nz),$$

and the complex conjugation operator K is defined by $(Kf)(z) = \bar{f}(-\bar{z})$. Set $\bar{W} = KW$. An element f in $S_k(N, \chi)$ is called a newform if it is an eigenfunction of \bar{W} and of all the Hecke operators T_n . An element f in $S_k(N, \chi)$ is called an oldform if there is an element f' in $S_k(N', \chi_{N'})$ such that $f(z) = f'(dz)$, where N', d are positive integers satisfying $f|N'$ and $dN'|N$ and where $\chi_{N'}$ is the Dirichlet character of modulus N' induced by χ .

Let f be a newform in $S_k(N, \chi)$. We normalize it so that its first Fourier coefficient is 1. Then it has the Fourier expansion

$$f(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda(n) e^{2\pi i n z}$$

with the Fourier coefficients equal to the eigenvalues of Hecke operators. Since f is an eigenfunction of the involution \bar{W} , we can assume that

$$\bar{W}f = \eta f$$

for constant η . The Hecke L -function associated with f is given by

$$L_f(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda(n)}{n^s}$$

for $\Re s > \frac{k+1}{2}$; see §7.2 of Iwaniec [7]. It has the Euler product

$$L_f(s) = \prod_p (1 - \lambda(p)p^{-s} + \chi(p)p^{k-1-2s})^{-1}. \tag{2}$$

If we denote

$$\xi_f(s) = \left(\frac{\sqrt{N}}{2\pi}\right)^s \Gamma\left(\frac{k-1}{2} + s\right) L_f\left(\frac{k-1}{2} + s\right), \tag{3}$$

then $\xi_f(s)$ is an entire function and satisfies the functional identity

$$\xi_f(s) = i^k \bar{\eta} \overline{\xi_f(1 - \bar{s})}.$$

When χ is primitive, we have $\eta = \tau(\bar{\chi})\lambda(N)N^{-k/2}$ with $\tau(\chi)$ being the Gauss sum for χ ; see Iwaniec [7].

Let

$$L_N(s) = \prod_{p \nmid N} \det |1 - T(p)p^{-s} + \chi(p)p^{k-1-2s} I|^{-1} \tag{4}$$

where I is the identity map acting on the space $S_k(N, \chi)$, and let

$$\xi_N(s) = N^{gs/2}(2\pi)^{-gs}\Gamma^g \left(\frac{k-1}{2} + s \right) L_N \left(\frac{k-1}{2} + s \right) \tag{5}$$

where g is the dimension of the space $S_k(N, \chi)$. It will be shown that $\xi_N(s)$ is an entire function, and that zeros of $\xi_N(s)$ in the strip $0 < \Re s < 1$ appear in pairs ρ and $1 - \bar{\rho}$.

Let

$$\tau_N(n) = \sum_{\rho} \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{\rho} \right)^{-n} \right] \tag{6}$$

for $n = 1, 2, \dots$, where the sum on ρ runs over all zeros of $\xi_N(s)$ taken in the order given by $|\Im \rho| < T$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$ with a zero of multiplicity ℓ appearing ℓ times in the list. If $\rho = 0$ is a zero of $\xi_N(s)$, then $(1 - 1/\rho)^{-n}$ in (6) is interpreted to be 0.

We let γ be Euler’s constant, $\Lambda(m)$ be $\ln p$ if m is a positive power of a prime p and 0 otherwise, and $d(m)$ be the number of positive divisors of m . For $m|N$ and $\mathfrak{f}|m$, we denote by ν_m the dimension of the subspace generated by all newforms in $S_k(m, \chi_m)$, where χ_m is the Dirichlet character of modulus m induced by the Dirichlet character χ of modulus N .

In this paper we obtain the following explicit formula for the $\tau_N(n)$ ’s, which generalizes the result in Li [12] where only the case $k = 2$ was considered. For a related result, see Lagarias [8].

Theorem 1 *Let $\tau_N(n)$ be given in (6). Then we have*

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_N(n) = & \frac{n}{2} \ln \left(N^{\nu_N} \prod_{\mathfrak{f}|m, m|N} m^{\nu_m d(N/m)} \right) - ng \left(\ln 2\pi + \gamma + \frac{2}{k+1} \right) \\ & - \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{(-1)^{l-1}}{(l-1)!} \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ (m,N)=1}}^{\infty} \frac{\Lambda(m)}{m^{\frac{k+1}{2}}} B(m) (\ln m)^{l-1} \\ & + ng \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{k+1}{l(2l+k+1)} + g \sum_{m=2}^n \binom{n}{m} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^m}{\left(l + \frac{k-1}{2}\right)^m} \end{aligned}$$

for all positive integers n , where $B(p^\ell) = \text{tr}(T(p^\ell)) - \chi(p)p^{k-1}\text{tr}(T(p^{\ell-2}))$ for $p \nmid N$ with $\text{tr}T(p^\ell)$ being the trace of the Hecke operator $T(p^\ell)$ acting on the space $S_k(N, \chi)$, and where the third term on the right side of the identity is interpreted as the limit

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{(-1)^{l-1}}{(l-1)!} \sum_{\substack{m < X \\ (m,N)=1}} \frac{\Lambda(m)}{m^{\frac{k+1}{2}}} B(m) (\ln m)^{l-1}$$

which exists.

In [2], Bombieri and Lagarias generalized a criterion of the author for the Riemann hypothesis [10] and obtained the following important theorem.

Theorem 2 (Bombieri-Lagarias [2]) *Let \mathcal{R} be a set of complex numbers ρ , whose elements have positive integral multiplicities assigned to them, such that $1 \notin \mathcal{R}$ and*

$$\sum_{\rho} \frac{1 + |\Re \rho|}{(1 + |\rho|)^2} < \infty.$$

Then the following conditions are equivalent:

1. $\Re \rho \leq \frac{1}{2}$ for every ρ in \mathcal{R} ;
2. $\sum_{\rho} \Re \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{\rho} \right)^{-n} \right] \geq 0$ for $n = 1, 2, \dots$.

As a corollary of Theorem 2 we obtain a criterion for the location of nontrivial zeros of Hecke L -functions associated with all Hecke eigenforms which form an orthonormal basis in $S_k(N, \chi)$.

Corollary 1 *All zeros of $\xi_N(s)$ in the strip $0 < \Re s < 1$ lie on the critical line $\Re s = 1/2$ if, and only if, $\tau_N(n) \geq 0$ for all positive integers n .*

This research started while the author attended the Workshop on Zeta-Functions and Associated Riemann Hypotheses, New York University, Manhattan, May 29 – June 1, 2002. He wants to thank the American Institute of Mathematics, Brian Conrey, and Peter Sarnak for the support. The author is grateful to the referee for pointing out several inaccuracies in the original version of the manuscript.

2. Preliminary Results

In Theorem 1 we need an explicit formula for the trace $\text{tr}T(p^\ell)$ of Hecke operators $T(p^\ell)$ acting on the space $S_k(N, \chi)$ for all primes $p \nmid N$ and for $\ell = 1, 2, \dots$. This formula is given by the Eichler-Selberg trace formula obtained in Oesterlé [15]. Denote by φ the Euler φ -function. Let

$$\psi(N) = N \prod_{p|N} (1 + 1/p),$$

and let $\chi(\sqrt{n}) = 0$ if n is not the square of an integer.

Theorem 3 (Théorème 3', [15]) *For every positive integer n , the trace $tr(T(n))$ of the Hecke operator $T(n)$ acting on the space $S_k(N, \chi)$ is given by*

$$\begin{aligned} tr(T(n)) &= n^{\frac{k}{2}-1} \chi(\sqrt{n}) \frac{k-1}{12} \psi(N) \\ &\quad - \sum_{t \in \mathbb{Z}, t^2 < 4n} \frac{\rho^{k-1} - \bar{\rho}^{k-1}}{\rho - \bar{\rho}} \sum_{\substack{m \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \\ \frac{t^2-4n}{m^2} = 0,1 \pmod{4}}} \frac{h((t^2 - 4n)/m^2)}{w((t^2 - 4n)/m^2)} \mu(t, n, m) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{0 < d|n} \min(d^{k-1}, (n/d)^{k-1}) \sum_{\substack{c|N \\ (c, \frac{N}{c}) | (\frac{N}{d}, \frac{n}{d} - d)}} \varphi((c, N/c)) \chi(y) \end{aligned}$$

where $\rho, \bar{\rho}$ are the roots of $x^2 - tx + n = 0$, where the integer y modulo $N/(c, N/c)$ is defined by $y \equiv d \pmod{c}, y \equiv n/d \pmod{N/c}$, where

$$\mu(t, n, m) = \frac{\psi(N)}{\psi(N/\gcd(N, m))} \sum_{\substack{x \pmod{N} \\ x^2 - tx + n \equiv 0 \pmod{N(N, m)}}} \chi(x),$$

and where $h(f)$ and $w(f)$ are respectively the class number and the number of units in the ring of integers of the imaginary quadratic field of discriminant $f < 0$.

Let f be a normalized newform in $S_k(N, \chi)$, and let $\xi_f(s)$ be given in (3). Put

$$\tau_f(n) = \sum_{\rho} \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{\rho} \right)^{-n} \right] \tag{7}$$

for $n = 1, 2, \dots$, where the sum is over all the zeros of $\xi_f(s)$ in the order given by $|\Im \rho| < T$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$ with a zero of multiplicity ℓ appearing ℓ times in the list.

Assume that f is a normalized newform in $S_k(N, \chi)$. For each prime number p , let α_p and β_p be the two roots of $T^2 - \lambda(p)T + \chi(p)p^{k-1}$ where $\lambda(p)$ is given as in (2). Put

$$b_f(p^m) = \begin{cases} \lambda(p)^m, & \text{if } p|N; \\ \alpha_p^m + \beta_p^m, & \text{if } (p, N) = 1. \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

The following theorem will be used in the proof of Theorem 1. It generalize a corresponding theorem in Li [11] for the L -series of an elliptic curve over \mathbb{Q} .

Theorem 4 *Assume that f is a normalized newform in $S_k(N, \chi)$. If $\tau_f(n)$ is given in (7),*

then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_f(n) = & n \left(\ln \frac{\sqrt{N}}{2\pi} - \gamma \right) - \sum_{j=1}^n \binom{n}{j} \frac{(-1)^{j-1}}{(j-1)!} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Lambda(l)}{l^{\frac{k+1}{2}}} b_f(l) (\ln l)^{j-1} \\ & + n \left(-\frac{2}{k+1} + \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{k+1}{l(2l+k+1)} \right) + \sum_{j=2}^n \binom{n}{j} (-1)^j \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(l + \frac{k-1}{2}\right)^j}. \end{aligned}$$

for $n = 1, 2, \dots$, where the second term on the right side of the identity is interpreted as the limit

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=1}^n \binom{n}{j} \frac{(-1)^{j-1}}{(j-1)!} \sum_{l < X} \frac{\Lambda(l)}{l^{\frac{k+1}{2}}} b_f(l) (\ln l)^{j-1}$$

which exists.

Lemma 1 (see [13]) *Let $F(x)$ be a function defined on the real line \mathbb{R} such that*

$$2F(x) = F(x + 0) + F(x - 0)$$

for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$, such that $F(x) \exp((\epsilon + 1/2)|x|)$ is integrable and of bounded variation on \mathbb{R} for a constant $\epsilon > 0$, and such that $(F(x) - F(0))/x$ is of bounded variation on \mathbb{R} . Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\rho} \Phi(\rho) = & 2F(0) \ln \frac{\sqrt{N}}{2\pi} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Lambda(n)}{n^{k/2}} [b_f(n)F(\ln n) + \bar{b}_f(n)F(-\ln n)] \\ & - \int_0^{\infty} \left((F(x) + F(-x)) \frac{e^{-kx/2}}{1 - e^{-x}} - 2F(0) \frac{e^{-x}}{x} \right) dx, \end{aligned}$$

where the sum on ρ runs over all zeros of $\xi_f(s)$ in the order given by $|\Im \rho| < T$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$, and

$$\Phi(s) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(x) e^{(s-1/2)x} dx.$$

Lemma 2 ([5] [6] [14]) *Let f be a newform in $S_k(N, \chi)$. Then there an absolute effective constant $c > 0$ such that $L_f(\frac{k-1}{2} + s)$ has no zeros in the region*

$$\left\{ s = \sigma + it : \sigma \geq 1 - \frac{c}{\ln(N + 1 + |t|)} \right\},$$

where L_f is given in (2).

Lemma 3 (Lemma 2 of [2]) *For $n = 1, 2, \dots$, let*

$$F_n(x) = \begin{cases} e^{x/2} \sum_{j=1}^n \binom{n}{j} \frac{x^{j-1}}{(j-1)!}, & \text{if } -\infty < x < 0; \\ n/2, & \text{if } x = 0; \\ 0, & \text{if } 0 < x. \end{cases}$$

Then

$$\Phi_n(s) = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{s}\right)^n$$

where Φ_n is related to F_n by the relation

$$\Phi_n(s) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F_n(x)e^{(s-1/2)x} dx.$$

Proof of Theorem 4. Since $\xi_f(s)$ is an entire function of order one and satisfies the functional identity $\xi_f(s) = i^k \bar{\eta} \xi_f(1 - \bar{s})$, we have

$$\xi_f(s) = i^k \bar{\eta} \bar{\xi}_f(1) \prod_{\rho} (1 - s/\rho)$$

where the product is over all the zeros of $\xi_f(s)$ in the order given by $|\Im \rho| < T$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$. If $\varphi_f(z) = \xi_f(1/(1 - z))$, then

$$\frac{\varphi'_f(z)}{\varphi_f(z)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \tau_f(n + 1) z^n \tag{9}$$

where the coefficients $\tau_f(n)$ are given in (7).

For a sufficiently large positive number X that is not an integer, let

$$F_{n,X}(x) = \begin{cases} F_n(x), & \text{if } -\ln X < x < \infty; \\ \frac{1}{2} F_n(-\ln X), & \text{if } x = -\ln X; \\ 0, & \text{if } -\infty < x < -\ln X \end{cases}$$

where

$$F_n(x) = \begin{cases} e^{x/2} \sum_{j=1}^n \binom{n}{j} \frac{x^{j-1}}{(j-1)!}, & \text{if } -\infty < x < 0; \\ n/2, & \text{if } x = 0; \\ 0, & \text{if } 0 < x. \end{cases}$$

Then $F_{n,X}(x)$ satisfies all conditions of Lemma 1. Let

$$\Phi_{n,X}(s) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F_{n,X}(x)e^{(s-1/2)x} dx.$$

By Lemma 1, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\rho} \Phi_{n,X}(\rho) &= 2F_{n,X}(0) \ln \frac{\sqrt{N}}{2\pi} - \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Lambda(l)}{l^{k/2}} [b_f(l)F_{n,X}(\ln l) + \bar{b}_f(l)F_{n,X}(-\ln l)] \\ &\quad - \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{F_{n,X}(x) + F_{n,X}(-x)}{1 - e^{-x}} e^{-kx/2} - 2F_{n,X}(0) \frac{e^{-x}}{x} \right) dx, \end{aligned}$$

where the sum on ρ runs over all zeros of $\xi_f(s)$ in the order given by $|\Im\rho| < T$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$. It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & \lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{\rho} \Phi_{n,X}(\rho) \\ &= n \left(\ln \frac{\sqrt{N}}{2\pi} - \gamma \right) - \sum_{j=1}^n \binom{n}{j} \frac{(-1)^{j-1}}{(j-1)!} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Lambda(l)}{l^{\frac{k+1}{2}}} \bar{b}_f(l) (\ln l)^{j-1} \\ &+ n \left(-\frac{2}{k+1} + \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{k+1}{l(2l+k+1)} \right) + \sum_{j=2}^n \binom{n}{j} (-1)^j \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(l + \frac{k-1}{2})^j}. \end{aligned}$$

Let

$$\Phi_n(s) = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{s} \right)^n.$$

Then Φ_n is related to F_n by the relation

$$\Phi_n(s) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F_n(x) e^{(s-1/2)x} dx$$

by Lemma 3. We have

$$\Phi_n(s) - \Phi_{n,X}(s) = \frac{X^{-s}}{s} \sum_{j=1}^n \binom{n}{j} \frac{(-\ln X)^{j-1}}{(j-1)!} + O\left(\frac{(\ln X)^{n-2}}{|s|^2} X^{-\Re s}\right) \tag{10}$$

for $\Re s > 0$.

Let ρ be any zero of $\xi_f(s)$. By Lemma 2, we have the de la Vallée-Poussin zero-free region

$$\frac{c}{\ln(N+1+|\rho|)} \leq \Re \rho \leq 1 - \frac{c}{\ln(N+1+|\rho|)}$$

for a positive constant c . An argument similar to that made in the proof of (3.9) of [2] shows that

$$\sum_{\rho} \frac{X^{-\Re \rho}}{|\rho|^2} \ll e^{-c'\sqrt{\ln X}} \tag{11}$$

for a positive constant c' .

Since

$$\sum_{\rho} \frac{X^{-\rho}}{\rho} = -\frac{1}{X} \sum_{\rho} \frac{X^{\bar{\rho}}}{\bar{\rho}} + O\left(e^{-c'\sqrt{\ln X}}\right),$$

and since

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(\ln X)^{j-1}}{X} \sum_{\rho} \frac{X^{\bar{\rho}}}{\bar{\rho}} = 0$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ by Theorem 4.2 and Theorem 5.2 of [14], we have

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} (\ln X)^{j-1} \sum_{\rho} \frac{X^{-\rho}}{\rho} = 0 \tag{12}$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$. It follows from (10), (11) and (12) that

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{\rho} \Phi_{n,X}(\rho) = \sum_{\rho} \Phi_n(\rho).$$

Since zeros of $\xi_f(s)$ appear in pairs ρ and $1 - \bar{\rho}$, we have

$$\sum_{\rho} \Phi_n(\bar{\rho}) = \tau_f(n)$$

for $n = 1, 2, \dots$. The stated identity then follows.

This completes the proof of the theorem. □

3. Proof of Theorem 1

A fundamental result of Hecke asserts that a basis $\{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_g\}$ in $S_k(N, \chi)$ exists which consists of eigenfunctions of all the Hecke operators $T(n)$ with $(n, N) = 1$; see Theorem 6.21 in Iwaniec [7]. We can assume that each f_j is either a normalized newform in $S_k(N, \chi)$ or coming from a normalized newform in a lower level. For $j = 1, \dots, g$, we choose $g_j = f_j$ if f_j is a normalized newform in $S_k(N, \chi)$, and $g_j = f'_j$ if f_j is an oldform in $S_k(N, \chi)$ and if f'_j is a normalized newform in $S_k(N', \chi_{N'})$ for some divisor N' of N with $\mathfrak{f}|N'$ such that $f_j(z) = f'_j(dz)$ for some positive integer $d|N/N'$, where $\chi_{N'}$ is the Dirichlet character of modulus N' induced by the Dirichlet character χ of modulus N .

Let

$$\xi_H(s) = \prod_{j=1}^g \xi_{g_j}(s) \tag{13}$$

where $\xi_{g_j}(s)$ is defined as in (3). Since $\xi_{g_j}(s)$ is an entire function and satisfies the functional identity $\xi_{g_j}(s) = w_j \bar{\xi}_{g_j}(1 - s)$ for a constant w_j , the function $\xi_H(s)$ is entire and satisfies the functional identity

$$\xi_H(s) = w \bar{\xi}_H(1 - s) \tag{14}$$

for a constant w . Put

$$\tau_H(n) = \sum_{j=1}^g \tau_{g_j}(n), \tag{15}$$

where $\tau_{g_j}(n)$ is defined similarly as in (7). If $\varphi_H(z) = \xi_H(1/(1 - z))$, then we have

$$\frac{\varphi'_H(z)}{\varphi_H(z)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \tau_H(n + 1) z^n \tag{16}$$

by (9).

Lemma 4 For all positive integers n with $(n, N) = 1$, we have

$$(T(n)f_j)(z) = \lambda_{g_j}(n)f_j(z)$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, g$, where $\lambda_{g_j}(n)$ is the eigenvalue of $T(n)$ acting on $g_j(z)$.

Proof. If f_j is a newform, the stated identity is trivially true.

Next, we assume that f_j is an oldform. Let g_j be a normalized newform in $S_k(N', \chi_{N'})$ for some divisor N' of N with $\mathfrak{f}|N'$ such that $f_j(z) = g_j(dz)$ for some positive integer $d|N/N'$. Since $(n, N) = 1$, by (1) we have

$$(T(n)f)(z) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{ad=n} \chi(a)a^k \sum_{0 \leq b < d} f\left(\frac{az+b}{d}\right)$$

for any function f in $S_k(N, \chi)$. Thus, we have

$$(T(n)f_j)(z) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\alpha\delta=n} \chi(\alpha)\alpha^k \sum_{0 \leq \beta < \delta} g_j\left(\frac{\alpha dz + d\beta}{\delta}\right).$$

Since $(n, N) = 1$, $d|N$ and $\alpha\delta = n$, we have $(\delta, d) = 1$. Let r_β be remainder of $d\beta$ modulo δ . Then $\{r_\beta : 0 \leq \beta < \delta\} = \{0, 1, \dots, \delta - 1\}$. Since $g_j \in S_k(N', \chi_{N'})$, we have

$$g_j\left(\frac{\alpha dz + d\beta}{\delta}\right) = g_j\left(\frac{\alpha dz + r_\beta}{\delta}\right).$$

Note that $\chi(t) = \chi_{N'}(t)$ for any positive integer t with $(t, N) = 1$. It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} (T(n)f_j)(z) &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\alpha\delta=n} \chi_{N'}(\alpha)\alpha^k \sum_{0 \leq \beta < \delta} g_j\left(\frac{\alpha dz + \beta}{\delta}\right) \\ &= (T(n)g_j)(w) = \lambda_{g_j}(n)g_j(w) = \lambda_{g_j}(n)f_j(z) \end{aligned}$$

where $w = dz$.

This completes the proof of the lemma. □

Lemma 5 Let $\xi_N(s)$ be given in (5). Then $\xi_N(s)$ is an entire function, and its zeros in the strip $0 < \Re s < 1$ appear in pairs ρ and $1 - \bar{\rho}$.

Proof. For $j = 1, 2, \dots, g$, let g_j be a normalized newform in $S_k(N_j, \chi_j)$ where χ_j is the Dirichlet character of modulus N_j induced by the Dirichlet character χ of modulus N . Then we can write

$$L_{g_j}(s) = \prod_p (1 - \lambda_{g_j}(p)p^{-s} + \chi_j(p)p^{k-1-2s})^{-1}. \tag{17}$$

Since f_1, f_2, \dots, f_g are eigenfunctions of all the Hecke operators $T(n)$ with $(n, N) = 1$, by Lemma 4 we have

$$\det |1 - T(p)p^{-s} + \chi(p)p^{k-1-2s}I| = \prod_{j=1}^g (1 - \lambda_{g_j}(p)p^{-s} + \chi(p)p^{k-1-2s})$$

for any prime $p \nmid N$. Let $L_N(s)$ be given in (4). Then we have

$$L_N(s) = \prod_{j=1}^g \prod_{p \nmid N} (1 - \lambda_{g_j}(p)p^{-s} + \chi(p)p^{k-1-2s})^{-1}.$$

Since $\chi(p) = \chi_j(p)$ for $j = 1, \dots, g$ when $p \nmid N$, we have

$$L_N(s) = \prod_{j=1}^g (L_{g_j}(s) \prod_{p|N_j} (1 - \lambda_{g_j}(p)p^{-s}) \prod_{p \nmid N_j, p|N} (1 - \lambda_{g_j}(p)p^{-s} + \chi_j(p)p^{k-1-2s})).$$

Since

$$\xi_{g_j}(s) = N_j^{s/2} (2\pi)^{-s} \Gamma\left(\frac{k-1}{2} + s\right) L_{g_j}\left(\frac{k-1}{2} + s\right),$$

we have

$$\xi_H(s) = A^{s/2} N^{gs/2} (2\pi)^{-gs} \Gamma^g\left(\frac{k-1}{2} + s\right) \prod_{j=1}^g L_{g_j}\left(\frac{k-1}{2} + s\right)$$

where $A = N^{-g} \prod_{j=1}^g N_j$. It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_N(s) &= \xi_H(s) A^{-s/2} \\ &\times \prod_{j=1}^g \left(\prod_{p|N_j} (1 - \lambda_{g_j}(p)p^{\frac{1-k}{2}-s}) \right) \prod_{p \nmid N_j, p|N} \left(1 - \lambda_{g_j}(p)p^{\frac{1-k}{2}-s} + \chi_j(p)p^{-2s} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

This implies that $\xi_N(s)$ is an entire function.

Assume $p|N_j$. By Theorem 3 of Li [9], if χ_j is not a character mod N_j/p then $|\lambda_{g_j}(p)| = p^{\frac{k-1}{2}}$, and if χ_j is a character mod N_j/p then $\lambda_{g_j}(p) = 0$ when $p^2|N_j$ and $|\lambda_{g_j}(p)| = p^{\frac{k-2}{2}}$ when $p^2 \nmid N_j$. It follows that all zeros of the function

$$\prod_{j=1}^g \prod_{p|N_j} \left(1 - \lambda_{g_j}(p)p^{\frac{1-k}{2}-s} \right)$$

lie on the lines $\Re s = 0, -1/2$.

Assume that $p \nmid N_j$ and $p|N$. Since the two roots of the polynomial $1 - \lambda_{g_j}(p)p^{\frac{1-k}{2}}z + \chi_j(p)z^2$ for $p \nmid N_j$ are of absolute value one by the Ramanujan conjecture which was proved in Théorème 8.2 of Deligne [4], all zeros of the function

$$\prod_{j=1}^g \prod_{p \nmid N_j, p|N} \left(1 - \lambda_{g_j}(p)p^{\frac{1-k}{2}-s} + \chi_j(p)p^{-2s} \right)$$

lie on the line $\Re s = 0$. Therefore, it follows from (14) and (18) that zeros of $\xi_N(s)$ in the critical strip $0 < \Re s < 1$ appear in pairs $\rho, 1 - \bar{\rho}$.

This completes the proof of the lemma. \square

Proof of Corollary 1. Let $\tau_N(n)$ be defined by (6) for all positive integers n . Since $\xi_H(s)$ is an entire function of order one, by (18) $\xi_N(s)$ is an entire function of order one. This implies that

$$\sum_{\rho} \frac{1 + |\Re \rho|}{(1 + |\rho|)^2} < \infty,$$

where the sum is over all zeros ρ of $\xi_N(s)$. Thus, conditions of Theorem 2 are satisfied. Since by (18) all zeros of $\xi_N(s)$ outside the strip $0 < \Re s < 1$ lie on the lines $\Re s = 0, -1/2$, Theorem 2 implies that all zeros of $\xi_N(s)$ in the critical strip $0 < \Re s < 1$ satisfy $\Re s \leq 1/2$ if, and only if, $\tau_N(n) \geq 0$ for all positive integers n . By Lemma 5, all zeros of $\xi_N(s)$ in the critical strip $0 < \Re s < 1$ appear in pairs ρ and $1 - \bar{\rho}$. Thus, $\tau_N(n) \geq 0$ for all positive integers n if, and only if, $\Re \rho \leq 1/2$ and $\Re(1 - \bar{\rho}) \leq 1/2$ for all zeros ρ of $\xi_N(s)$ in the critical strip $0 < \Re s < 1$. That is, all zeros of $\xi_N(s)$ in the strip $0 < \Re s < 1$ lie on the critical line $\Re s = 1/2$ if, and only if, $\tau_N(n) \geq 0$ for all positive integers n .

This completes the proof of the corollary. \square

Lemma 6 *Let p be a prime, and let α be a complex number. Then we have*

$$1 - \alpha p^{-s} = c_p s^{\epsilon_p} \prod_{\rho} (1 - s/\rho)$$

where the product on ρ is over all nonzero zeros of $1 - \alpha p^{-s}$ taken in the order given by $|\rho| < T$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$ and where $c_p = 1 - \alpha, \epsilon_p = 0$ if $\alpha \neq 1$ and $c_p = \ln p, \epsilon_p = 1$ if $\alpha = 1$.

Proof. Since $1 - \alpha p^{-s}$ is an entire function of order one, by Hadamard's factorization theorem there is a constant a such that

$$1 - \alpha p^{-s} = c_p e^{as} s^{\epsilon_p} \prod_{\rho} (1 - s/\rho) e^{s/\rho} \tag{19}$$

where the product is over all nonzero zeros of $1 - \alpha p^{-s}$. Let $\alpha = e^{it}$ with $0 \leq \Re t < 2\pi$. Then the zeros of $1 - \alpha p^{-s}$ are $i(t + 2k\pi)/\ln p, k = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$. Since

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{-i \ln p}{t + 2k\pi} + \frac{-i \ln p}{t - 2k\pi} \right) = 2it \ln p \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2k\pi)^2 - t^2}$$

is absolutely convergent, by using (19) we can write

$$1 - \alpha p^{-s} = c_p e^{hs} s^{\epsilon_p} \prod_{\rho} (1 - s/\rho) \tag{20}$$

for a constant h , where the product runs over all nonzero zeros ρ of $1 - \alpha p^{-s}$ taken in the order given by $|\rho| < T$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$. By taking the logarithmic derivative of both sides of (20) with respect to s we get

$$\frac{\alpha \ln p}{p^s - \alpha} = h + \frac{\epsilon_p}{s} + \sum_{\rho} \frac{1}{s - \rho}. \tag{21}$$

By letting $s \rightarrow \infty$ in (21) we find that $h = 0$. Then the stated identity follows from (20).

This completes the proof of the lemma. □

Lemma 7 *Let α, p be given in Lemma 6, and let $s = (1 - z)^{-1}$. Then we have*

$$\frac{d}{dz} \ln(1 - \alpha p^{-s}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{\rho} [1 - (1 - 1/\rho)^{-n-1}] \right) z^n$$

for z in a small neighborhood of the origin, where the sum on ρ is over all zeros of $1 - \alpha p^{-s}$ taken in the order given by $|\rho| < T$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof. By Lemma 6 we have

$$\frac{d}{dz} \ln(1 - \alpha p^{-s}) = \frac{\epsilon_p}{1 - z} + \sum_{\rho} \frac{1}{(1 - \rho) + \rho z} \frac{1}{1 - z} \tag{22}$$

where the sum on ρ is over all nonzero zeros of $1 - \alpha p^{-s}$. Since

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{(1 - \rho) + \rho z} \frac{1}{1 - z} &= \frac{1}{1 - \rho} \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{-\rho}{1 - \rho} \right)^k z^k \right\} \left\{ \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} z^l \right\} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [1 - (1 - 1/\rho)^{-n-1}] z^n \end{aligned}$$

for z in a small neighborhood of the origin, the stated identity follows from (22). Note that, if $s = \rho = 0$ is a zero of $1 - \alpha p^{-s}$, then $(1 - 1/\rho)^{-n}$ is interpreted to be 0 for all positive integers n .

This completes the proof of the lemma. □

Remark. By (18), Lemma 7, (9) and (13) we have

$$\frac{d}{dz} \log(A^{s/2} \xi_N(s)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \tau_N(n + 1) z^n$$

with $s = (1 - z)^{-1}$, where the $\tau_N(n)$'s are given in (6). Then, by Lemma 5, to prove that all zeros of $\xi_N(s)$ in the strip $0 < \Re s < 1$ lie on the critical line $\Re s = 1/2$ it is enough to find an upper bound for each $\tau_N(n)$ which implies that the above series is analytic for $|z| < 1$.

Lemma 8 Let α, p be given in Lemma 6, and let $s = (1 - z)^{-1}$. Then we have

$$\frac{d}{dz} \ln(1 - \alpha p^{-s}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n+1}{j+1} \frac{(-1)^j}{j!} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln p}{p^m} \alpha^m (\ln p^m)^j \right) z^n$$

for z in a small neighborhood of the origin.

Proof. Let m be any positive integer. By using mathematical induction on n , we can show that

$$\frac{d^n}{dz^n} [(1 - z)^{-m} p^{-ks}]_{|z=0} = p^{-k} \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n}{j} (n + m - 1) \cdots (j + m) (-\ln p^k)^j \tag{23}$$

for $n = 1, 2, \dots$. By using the formula (23) with $m = 2$ we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dz} \ln(1 - \alpha p^{-s}) &= (1 - z)^{-2} \ln p \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha^k p^{-ks} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{n!} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha^k \frac{\ln p}{p^k} \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n}{j} (n + 1) \cdots (j + 2) (-\ln p^k)^j \right) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} z^n \left(\sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n+1}{j+1} \frac{(-1)^j}{j!} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln p}{p^k} \alpha^k (\ln p^k)^j \right). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the lemma. □

Lemma 9 Let p be a prime, and let α be a complex number. Then we have

$$\sum_{\rho} [1 - (1 - 1/\rho)^{-n}] = \sum_{j=1}^n \binom{n}{j} \frac{(-1)^{j-1}}{(j-1)!} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln p}{p^m} \alpha^m (\ln p^m)^{j-1}$$

for $n = 1, 2, \dots$, where the sum on ρ is over all zeros of $1 - \alpha p^{-s}$ taken in the order given by $|\Im \rho| < T$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$ with a zero of multiplicity ℓ appearing ℓ times in the list.

Proof. The stated identity follows from Lemma 7 and Lemma 8. □

Lemma 10 For $n = 1, 2, \dots$, we have

$$\tau_N(n) = \sum_{j=1}^g \tau_{g_j}(n) + \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{(-1)^{l-1}}{(l-1)!} \sum_{(m,N) > 1, m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Lambda(m)}{m^{\frac{k+1}{2}}} \left(\sum_{j=1}^g b_{g_j}(m) \right) (\ln m)^{l-1}$$

where $b_{g_j}(m)$ is given as in (8).

Proof. Let $\tau_H(n)$ be given in (15). By (7), (13) and (18) we have

$$\tau_N(n) = \tau_H(n) + \sum_{j=1}^g \left\{ \sum_{p|N_j} \sum_{\rho_j} [1 - (1 - 1/\rho_j)^{-n}] + \sum_{p \nmid N_j, p|N} \sum_{\alpha_j} [1 - (1 - 1/\alpha_j)^{-n}] \right\}, \quad (24)$$

where the sum on ρ_j is over all zeros of $1 - \lambda_{g_j}(p)p^{\frac{1-k}{2}-s}$ with $p|N_j$ and where the sum on α_j is over all zeros of $1 - \lambda_{g_j}(p)p^{\frac{1-k}{2}-s} + \chi_j(p)p^{-2s}$ with $p \nmid N_j, p|N$. By Lemma 9 we have

$$\sum_{\rho_j} [1 - (1 - 1/\rho_j)^{-n}] = \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{(-1)^{l-1}}{(l-1)!} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln p}{p^{\frac{k+1}{2}m}} b_{g_j}(p^m) (\ln p^m)^{l-1} \quad (25)$$

and

$$\sum_{\alpha_j} [1 - (1 - 1/\alpha_j)^{-n}] = \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{(-1)^{l-1}}{(l-1)!} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln p}{p^{\frac{k+1}{2}m}} b_{g_j}(p^m) (\ln p^m)^{l-1}. \quad (26)$$

It follows from (25) and (26) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{p|N_j} \sum_{\rho_j} [1 - (1 - 1/\rho_j)^{-n}] + \sum_{p \nmid N_j, p|N} \sum_{\alpha_j} [1 - (1 - 1/\alpha_j)^{-n}] \\ &= \sum_{p|N} \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{(-1)^{l-1}}{(l-1)!} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln p}{p^{\frac{k+1}{2}m}} b_{g_j}(p^m) (\ln p^m)^{l-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

By (27) we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j=1}^g \left(\sum_{p|N_j} \sum_{\rho_j} [1 - (1 - 1/\rho_j)^{-n}] + \sum_{p \nmid N_j, p|N} \sum_{\alpha_j} [1 - (1 - 1/\alpha_j)^{-n}] \right) \\ &= \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{(-1)^{l-1}}{(l-1)!} \sum_{(m,N) > 1, m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Lambda(m)}{m^{\frac{k+1}{2}}} \left(\sum_{j=1}^g b_{g_j}(m) \right) (\ln m)^{l-1}. \end{aligned}$$

The stated identity then follows from (24). □

We define an operator S acting on the space $S_k(N, \chi)$ by

$$\begin{aligned} S(1) &= 2I \\ S(p) &= T(p) \\ S(p^m) &= T(p^m) - \chi(p)p^{k-1}T(p^{m-2}) \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

for $m = 2, 3, \dots$

Lemma 11 *For each prime $p \nmid N$, the trace $\text{tr}(S(p^m))$ of $S(p^m)$ acting on the space $S_k(N, \chi)$ is given by*

$$\text{tr}(S(p^m)) = \sum_{j=1}^g b_{g_j}(p^m)$$

for $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

Proof. Let p be any prime. It follows from the recursion formula (see (6.25) in Iwaniec [7])

$$T(p^{m+1}) = T(p)T(p^m) - \chi(p)p^{k-1}T(p^{m-1})$$

that

$$S(p^{m+1}) = S(p)S(p^m) - \chi(p)p^{k-1}S(p^{m-1})$$

for $m = 1, 2, \dots$.

Let p be any prime not dividing N . When $m = 0$, we have

$$S(p^m)f_j = 2f_j = b_{g_j}(p^m)f_j.$$

When $m = 1$, we have

$$S(p^m)f_j = T(p)f_j = \lambda_{g_j}(p)f_j = b_{g_j}(p^m)f_j$$

by Lemma 4. Assume that

$$S(p^m)f_j = b_{g_j}(p^m)f_j$$

for all integers $m \leq l$. When $m = l + 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} S(p^m)f_j &= (S(p)S(p^l) - \chi(p)p^{k-1}S(p^{l-1}))f_j \\ &= (b_{g_j}(p)b_{g_j}(p^l) - \chi(p)p^{k-1}b_{g_j}(p^{l-1}))f_j \\ &= b_{g_j}(p^m)f_j. \end{aligned}$$

By mathematical induction the identity

$$S(p^m)f_j = b_{g_j}(p^m)f_j$$

holds for all nonnegative integers m . Since $\{f_1, \dots, f_g\}$ is a basis for $S_k(N, \chi)$, we have

$$tr(S(p^m)) = \sum_{j=1}^g b_{g_j}(p^m)$$

for $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$.

This completes the proof of the lemma. □

From Lemma 11 and the definition (28) we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 2 *For each prime $p \nmid N$, we have*

$$\sum_{j=1}^g b_{g_j}(p^m) = tr(T(p^m)) - \chi(p)p^{k-1} tr(T(p^{m-2}))$$

for $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$.

Proof of Theorem 1. By Lemma 10 we have

$$\tau_N(n) = \sum_{j=1}^g \tau_{g_j}(n) + \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{(-1)^{l-1}}{(l-1)!} \sum_{(m,N)>1, m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Lambda(m)}{m^{\frac{k+1}{2}}} \left(\sum_{j=1}^g b_{g_j}(m) \right) (\ln m)^{l-1} \tag{29}$$

for $n = 1, 2, \dots$. Since g_j is a normalized newform in $S_k(N_j, \chi)$, by Theorem 4 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{g_j}(n) = & n \left(\ln \frac{\sqrt{N_j}}{2\pi} - \gamma \right) - \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{(-1)^{l-1}}{(l-1)!} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Lambda(m)}{m^{\frac{k+1}{2}}} b_{g_j}(m) (\ln m)^{l-1} \\ & + n \left(-\frac{2}{k+1} + \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{k+1}{l(2l+k+1)} \right) + \sum_{m=2}^n \binom{n}{m} (-1)^m \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(l + \frac{k-1}{2})^m}. \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

By using (29) and (30) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_N(n) = & \frac{n}{2} \ln(N_1 \cdots N_g) - \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{(-1)^{l-1}}{(l-1)!} \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ (m,N)=1}}^{\infty} \frac{\Lambda(m)}{m^{\frac{k+1}{2}}} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^g b_{g_j}(m) \right\} (\ln m)^{l-1} \\ & - ng \left[\ln 2\pi + \gamma + \frac{2}{k+1} - \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{k+1}{l(2l+k+1)} \right] + g \sum_{m=2}^n \binom{n}{m} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^m}{(l + \frac{k-1}{2})^m}. \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

By the argument in the proof of Theorem 5 in Atkin and Lehner [1], we have

$$\prod_{N_j \neq N, 1 \leq j \leq g} N_j = \prod_{m|N, \not\equiv 1 \pmod{m}} m^{\nu_m d(N/m)}. \tag{32}$$

We also have

$$\prod_{N_j = N, 1 \leq j \leq g} N_j = N^{\nu_N}. \tag{33}$$

By (31), (32) and (33) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_N(n) = & \frac{n}{2} \ln \left(N^{\nu_N} \prod_{\not\equiv 1 \pmod{m}, m|N} m^{\nu_m d(N/m)} \right) - ng \left(\ln 2\pi + \gamma + \frac{2}{k+1} \right) \\ & - \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{(-1)^{l-1}}{(l-1)!} \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ (m,N)=1}}^{\infty} \frac{\Lambda(m)}{m^{\frac{k+1}{2}}} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^g b_{g_j}(m) \right\} (\ln m)^{l-1} \\ & + ng \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{k+1}{l(2l+k+1)} + g \sum_{m=2}^n \binom{n}{m} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^m}{(l + \frac{k-1}{2})^m}. \end{aligned}$$

The stated identity then follows from Corollary 2.

This completes the proof of Theorem 1. □

Remark. If χ is a primitive Dirichlet character of modulus N , we define

$$L_N(s) = \prod_p \det |1 - T(p)p^{-s} + \chi(p)p^{k-1-2s} I|^{-1}$$

where I is the identity map acting on the space $S_k(N, \chi)$ and where the product on p runs over all prime numbers. Let

$$\xi_N(s) = N^{gs/2} (2\pi)^{-gs} \Gamma^g \left(\frac{k-1}{2} + s \right) L_N \left(\frac{k-1}{2} + s \right),$$

where g denotes the dimension of the space $S_k(N, \chi)$. Since the space $S_k(N, \chi)$ contains only newforms (see §6.7 of Iwaniec [7]), we have $\xi_N(s) = \xi_H(s)$ by (18). Hence, $\xi_N(s)$ is an entire function and satisfies the functional identity

$$\xi_N(s) = w \overline{\xi_N(1 - \bar{s})},$$

where w is a constant.

References

- [1] A. O. L. Atkin and J. Lehner, *Hecke operators on $\Gamma_0(m)$* , Math. Ann. **185** (1970), 134–160.
- [2] E. Bombieri and J. C. Lagarias, *Complements to Li's criterion for the Riemann hypothesis*, J. Number Theory **77** (1999), 274–287.
- [3] J. B. Conrey and A. Ghosh, *Turán inequalities and zeros of Dirichlet series associated with certain cusp forms*, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc. **342** (1994), 407–419.
- [4] P. Deligne, *La Conjecture de Weil. I*, IHES Publ. Math. **43** (1974), 273–307.
- [5] S. S. Gelbart, *Automorphic Forms on Adele Groups*, Princeton University Press, (1975).
- [6] J. Hoffstein and D. Ramakrishnan, *Siegel zeros and cusp forms*, Internat. Math. Res. Notices **6** (1995), 279–308.
- [7] H. Iwaniec, *Topics in Classical Automorphic Forms*, Amer. Math. Soc., Providence, RI (1997).
- [8] J. C. Lagarias, *Li coefficients for automorphic L-functions*, Annales Inst. Fourier **57** (2007), to appear.
- [9] W. Li, *Newforms and functional equations*, Math. Ann. **212** (1975), 285–315.
- [10] Xian-Jin Li, *The positivity of a sequence of numbers and the Riemann hypothesis*, J. Number Theory **65** (1997), 325–333.
- [11] Xian-Jin Li, *Explicit formulas for Dirichlet and Hecke L-functions*, Illinois J. Math. **48** (2004), 491–503.
- [12] Xian-Jin Li, *An arithmetic formula for certain coefficients of the Euler product of Hecke polynomials*, J. Number Theory **113** (2005), 175–200.
- [13] J.-F. Mestre, *Formules explicites et minoration de conducteurs de variétés algébriques*, Compositio Math. **58** (1986), 209–232.
- [14] C. J. Moreno, *Explicit formulas in the theory of automorphic forms*, Number Theory Day, Lecture Notes in Math., no. 626, Springer, Berlin, 1977 73–216.
- [15] J. Oesterlé, *Sur la trace des opérateurs de Hecke*, Thèse de Docteur 3è cycle, Université de Paris-Sud, Centre d'Orsay, 1977.